

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

On-farm economic evaluation of the reduction in fertilization and the application of biostimulants in a cereal-based crop rotation

This study looks at the reduction in fertilization the use of and plant growth promoting microorganisms in SE Spain's rainfed cereal production as an alternative to increase nutrients' availability and crop yields. The crop rotation considered includes rye and wheat, cultivated sequentially along two years (2020-2022).

The experimental design comprises four treatments: the control treatment with a conventional fertilization scheme based on organic pellets as cover fertilization and pig slurry (T1); a reduction of fertilization (T2); a reduction of fertilization combined with the application of plant growth-promoting bacteria and fungus (T3); and a reduction of fertilization combined with the application of plant growth-promoting

bacteria (T4). Fertilization was reduced by 30% in the crop cycles. The applied biofertilizers are BACTONECO™, a combination of nitrogen fixing and phosphorus and potassium solubilizing bacterial strains, and NUVE™, a mixture of bacteria and non-mycorrhizal fungi, both produced by the Spanish firm Fyneco®.

Our results suggest that reducing fertilization is a profitable and sustainable alternative, as crop yields are not negatively affected but fertilization costs are notably reduced, thus increasing crop profitability. On the other hand, the application of the two biostimulants have not been found to be profitable alternatives, as the increase in costs is not compensated by an increase in crop yields, at least in the short run.

Experimental treatment	Revenue (€/ha)	Direct costs (€/ha)	Gross margin (€/ha)
T1: Control 100% Fertilization	835	942	-107
T2: Reduced Fertilization	884	526	358
T3: Reduced Fertilization + NUVE™	856	696	160
T4: Reduced Fertilization + BACTONECO™	852	688	164

1. Average value of sales revenue, direct production costs and gross margin by experimental treatment for the whole crop rotation.

KEYWORDS

Economic profitability, gross margin, fertilizers, cereal cropping, nutrient-solubilizing bacteria, mycorrhizal fungi

AUTHORSHIP

Javier Calatrava, Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena (UPCT), Spain

David Martínez-Granados, Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena (UPCT), Spain

Irene Ollio, Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena (UPCT), Spain

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

This factsheet is produced as part of the SoildiverAgro project. Although the author has worked on the best information available, neither the author nor the EU shall in any event be liable for any loss, damage or injury incurred directly or indirectly in relation to the project.